

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most quite a few North American bears. The commonest is the American black bear, followed by the brown bear after which the polar bear. Found all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Might be darkish or light brown (cinnamon), typically even white. Not all the time black in color. 900,000 and not threatened. □□Location: The American black bear could be discovered throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Nonetheless, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected underneath the U.S. □□ Size: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to six feet in size. □□ Options: Most black bears are black, however their fur can vary from darkish brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on rare events. They've pointed ears and a straight face. Of all the bear species black bears are a few of the best at climbing bushes. Their relatively smaller measurement and shorter claws make them fast and nimble to climb bushes for protection, food, and even hibernation. Nearly all of their weight-reduction plan is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Eating regimen: Their diversified eating regimen gives them the ability to live in a big range of habitats. They also eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Harmful? They're the most probably bear to be encountered in the backcountry. And yes, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the two subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are found within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Brown bears are the most widespread of all bear species, found within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Grizzlies are accountable for nearly all bear attacks in North America, with 46 per yr. Though their conservation standing is "least concern", their spread-out nature and reduced habitat make most of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a large number of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a big construct, a dish-shaped face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the ideas, which led to the identify of probably the most well-known subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and some even hunt younger mammals akin to elk and moose. Their shade varies from light blonde to dark brown. The 2 subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□Location: Grizzly bears are discovered within the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Measurement: Adults weigh 400 to 790 pounds, are 6.5 feet long, and have a shoulder height of 3. Three toes. □□ Food plan: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been known to prey on large mammals. Coastal grizzlies tend to be bigger than these discovered within the Rocky Mountains due to a richer diet. Annually there are 46 attacks and 6 deaths. □□ Harmful? Known for his or her aggressive behavior, grizzlies are answerable for essentially the most bear assaults in North America. □□Location: Kodiak bears are solely discovered on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Measurement: Kodiak bears are virtually as large as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1,400 pounds, eight ft lengthy, and four toes tall on the shoulder. □□ Eating regimen: Their weight loss program is similar to mainland grizzly bears. Nevertheless, attributable to extra plentiful food sources, the islands can help a denser bear inhabitants. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to develop into their [very very big teddy bear](#)

very own subspecies. This has led to a more complicated social construction which ends up in less battle between bears. □□ Harmful? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears will be aggressive. Attributable to their isolation, there is just one assault on humans every other year. Largest species of bear in the world weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Weight loss program is usually made up of meat, often from seals. □□Location: Polar bears are the most important bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur appears white but is definitely clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears range within the snow-lined arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Dimension: Adult polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and may be 7 to 10 ft tall. They're a threatened species resulting from loss of habitat from climate change. Regardless of their enormous dimension polar bears may be quick, maintaining a 6 mph pace within the water. □□ Features: In comparison with other bears, polar bears have a slimmer body, slender head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps won Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph pace! □□ Weight loss program: Their food plan consists mostly of animals, particularly seals which they will odor from a mile away. Although they seem white, their fur is actually clear and their pores and skin is black. □□ Dangerous? Polar bears can be extremely dangerous. They see people as potential prey. Attacks are uncommon due to the remote nature of their habitat. Identified for its cream shade chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of many smaller bears. Easy to tame and often common in circuses. □□Location: The Asian black bear is present in forests and shrublands across Asia from Iran to Japan. The population is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is taken into account weak. □□ Size: One of the smaller species, adults weigh

around 300 pounds and stand forty seven to seventy five inches tall. □□ Eating regimen: Relying on the season it commonly feeds on small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits, berries, seeds, insects, and honey. Assaults on people are rising as people encroach on their habitat. □□ Dangerous? They're certainly one of the easiest bears to tame (and subsequently frequent in circuses), but Asian black bears are extra aggressive than their North American counterparts. Found only in China. 99% of its food plan is bamboo. In reality, the second person in history to receive a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear whereas protecting his sheep. Recognized for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped physique. □□ Location: Pandas are discovered only in China. Solely 1,500 to 2,000 stay in the wild and they're thought of a susceptible species. □□ Measurement: Pandas weigh round 300 pounds and might be over 4 ft tall, a powerful feat contemplating they weigh only about 3.5 ounces at beginning. It additionally has a close cousin, the Qinling panda which has the identical sample in mild brown and white. □□ Diet: In contrast to other bears the panda's weight loss program is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. □□ Options: The enormous panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped physique. All that fibrous bamboo keeps them common: they poop over forty occasions a day! □□ Harmful? Assaults are rare however dangerous, given that pandas have considered one of the highest chunk forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing fifty five to 143 pounds. Found in South East Asia. Eight to 10-inch lengthy tongue for slurping up insects and honey. □□ Location: The Solar bear is discovered within the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It's the least studied bear and. Its inhabitants is unsure but considered weak and on the decline as a consequence of loss of habitat and poaching. Sun bears are hunted for his or her gallbladders and other physique elements used in conventional medicines. □□ Measurement: They stand only 39 to 55 inches and weigh 55 to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. □□ Options: Solar bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a brief snout. They are named for his or her pale, horseshoe-formed chest patch that looks like a rising solar. They also eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. □□ Weight loss program: Solar bears tear apart trees and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." In truth, they've an incredibly lengthy tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. □□ Dangerous? On account of its shy nature, attacks are uncommon. Lengthy, shaggy fur and mane gave them the title sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. □□ Location: The Sloth bear is discovered in the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining inhabitants of lower than 20,000, they're considered weak. □□ Measurement: They are 55 to 75 inches lengthy and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. □□ Features: With their long shaggy fur and mane, they're simple to tell aside from different Asiatic bears. In actuality, they're very fast and can out-gallop humans. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging the other way up from timber. They're noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their big curved claws. □□ Food plan: Their diet consists of termites, ants, and fruit. □□ Harmful? They're one of the vital aggressive bears, with probably the most assaults on people, largely due to surprise encounters. They blow the dust around with huge puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they can be heard 600 ft away. Sloth bears stand their floor if threatened and do not combine well with rhinos and elephants, often charging at one another when in proximity. Solely South American bear. World's final short-confronted bear. The title "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings round their eyes that appear like glasses. This susceptible species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are found within the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. □□ Dimension: They're mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing 47 to 79 inches tall. □□ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's final quick-faced bear and the only bear native to South America. □□ Features: The name "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that sometimes appear to be glasses. They spend most of their time in bushes the place they construct nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard valuable fruit and carcasses. □□ Weight loss plan: Spectacled bears are largely herbivores with a food plan consisting of mostly cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, however they'll opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. □□ Harmful? Dwelling in distant mountains, these shy bears stands out as the least harmful of all bear species. Their our bodies are smaller than polar bears however larger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a rare hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that happens in both nature and captivity. Grolar bear habits is closer to the polar bear. They function the long necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they've been documented stomping toys, similar to how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably at the London Zoo in 1859, but haven't been confirmed in the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot but DNA assessments had been unable to find out what type of bear it was. Adorable koalas are usually not bears, they're burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears both, they are indestructible, microscopic animals that may survive in house. Most bear assaults happen when a bear is startled

or defending their cubs. Purple pandas? They're in their own family which are closer cousins with skunks and raccoons than bears.

1. **BEWARE OF YOUR SURROUNDINGS.** Look ahead to bear scat and bear tracks which will indicate a bear is nearby, during which case you wish to be additional vigilant. Listed here are just a few tips you can use to prevent bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies secure.
2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you're right here so they don't unintentionally startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack.
3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** While you'll have great intentions, a bear is prone to feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself.
3. **Safe YOUR SCENTED Items (AT CAMP).** For those who see a bear, do not attempt to strategy or feed it. This consists of food, but additionally your toiletries, for example. Whichever technique you select, make sure it's a minimum of 200 feet away out of your tent so you do not entice bears to your campsite.
4. **Keep CALM.** When you meet a bear, do not run. Attempt to make your self look as big as doable, waving your arms above your head. You may as well extend a jacket above your head to make your self look bigger. Lock these items in a bear canister or use a bear bag to hang them up in a tree. Don't scream or try to scare the bear.
5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A last RESORT).** Speak to it calmly and slowly back away. Full instruction on how to use bear spray right here. If the bear is dangerously shut (30 feet) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming barely downward.
6. **Combat Back.** If all else fails and a bear attacks you, don't play useless.

Which bear is the most important? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.0 to 8.4 ft long, and 4.0 to 5.25 feet tall, the largest bear by both size and weight is the polar bear. The biggest ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Struggle back with all your strength and hope that it'll again down. Which bear is probably the most harmful? All bears are dangerous if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is understood for probably the most attacks. When in bear country, it's all the time smart to carry bear spray. It's effectively deserved, especially when cubs are round. Annually there are approximately forty six grizzly assaults, 6 leading to death. In North America, grizzly bears have the most fearsome fame. Which bear is the strongest? While you're most more likely to see an American black bear, on common there is only one attack per yr. By way of raw chew power, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's bite reigns supreme. All bears are robust and to not be messed with. When using the chew drive quotient (bite energy relative to measurement), the solar bear packs probably the most punch. Originally named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub found within the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to flee the fireplace however sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Soon after he grew to become an icon and to this present day is the star of the longest-running public service announcement marketing campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear known for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. Extra importantly Yogi Bear has inspired countless via-hikers to try and grasp the art of "yogi-ing", the act of not fairly begging but receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, although he has some traits of the Asian black bear. He is an easygoing, pleasant bear who lives a responsibility-free lifestyle. He additionally might be the first bear to obtain his pilot's license. Before he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son typically would visit at the London Zoo. Winnie is brief for "Winnipeg," the city in Canada near the place he was from. Chris also wrote Find out how to Hike the Appalachian Path. Equal elements backpacking food and ultralight gear. After thru-hiking the Appalachian Trail, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to provide quick, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic tips, guides and the way-to's in your inbox each two weeks.

